

Assessment of Socioeconomic Impacts of Participatory Forest Management in Muzaffarabad

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SUMMARY

The study looks into the impact of participatory forest management (PFM) projects in Azad Jammu and Kashmir, specifically in the Muzaffarabad district. Despite the regions nearly three decades of PFM programs, thorough data on their evaluation is limited. The study uses a multistage random sampling technique to survey 84 households/respondents in villages with active PFM initiatives. The study demonstrates that PFM programs have resulted in significant improvements in both community socioeconomic situations and environmental protection through organized questionnaires and informal talks with local populations and Forest Department workers. Through the sale of forest products, these interventions provided income to 42% of respondents, with many earning up to Rs. 30,000 per year. Furthermore, the study emphasizes increasing engagement in forest management activities, the importance of enhancing female community organizations and strengthening capacity building, and the importance of democratizing community organization formation. Respondents showed general satisfaction, but asked for more incentives and a more democratic approach for forming community organizations. The study also emphasizes the importance of forests in providing livelihood assistance, with 75 percent of respondents benefiting from PFM efforts. Positive benefits included increased fuel wood and feed resources, infrastructural development, job prospects, and domestic business opportunities. Furthermore, the study highlights the improved forest condition, reduced soil erosion, increased perennial water flow, and better drinking water quality as a result of PFM efforts.

Keywords: PFM, Sustainable, Reforestation of Blanks, Integrated Land Management Project

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INTRODUCTION

Pakistan is a forest deficient country with an extremely inadequate natural forest cover of approximately 5.2% that amounts to 4.57 million hectares (Jan, 1993). Unsustainable human activity has led to problems, which can be broadly referred to

as, the quantitative and qualitative decline of the forests and related resources. Quantitatively, Pakistan's total forest area between 1990 and 2001 was measured as 2,755,000 ha and 2,361,000 ha respectively representing annual reduction of 38,000 ha (FAO, 2000; Shahbaz and Shah, 2010; Arshad, 2012). Increasing human demands due to massive increase in population are damaging the natural resources based on water and air upon which all the development ultimately depends. Industrialized areas have largely contributed to the environmental degradation (Ejaz, 1998).

The most of natural coniferous forests are located in mountainous and sub-mountainous parts of NWFP now (KPK), Northern Areas and Azad Jammu & Kashmir (AJK) (UNDP, 2002; Shahbaz and Shah, 2010; Arshad, 2012). In Pakistan forests produce only 0.3 million cubic meters timber and 0.4 million cubic meters of firewood. The estimated annual demand is 1.9 million cubic meters of firewood. The shortage is met from farmlands and by import of wood and wood products (Mohammad, 1989). Azad Jammu & Kashmir has 770,000 hectares forest area (43% of the total area) out of which 84700 hectare area is commercial forest area i.e. 11% (Forest and Forestry statistics AJ&K Forest Department, 2002). Located in foot hills of Himalayas, AJK has an area of 1.33 million ha with elevation range of 360 meters (m) to 6325 m. It is well endowed with forests, range lands, agriculture fields, rivers, springs and diversified flora and fauna (Altaf *et al.*, 2023; Iftikhar *et al.*, 2023). The total population of AJK is estimated at 3.2 million with a density of about 220 people/square kilometer. Some 88% households (averaging 7 persons) are rural. Due to limited employment possibilities, male out migration is common. Although literacy rate is 55%, the existing education and health facilities are extremely limited (IFAD, 2003). Existing forest is insufficient to meet needs of Forest Department and communities, growing population has led pressure on natural resources especially shamlats and state forests (Mamoona, 2009; Shahbaz and Shah, 2010; Arshad, 2012).

Forest resources are under pressure due to several reasons. Forest Department thinks, over exploitation by communities is main problem. However, different projects experience that community participation can prove essential to retain the forest cover (Mamoona, 2009; Shahbaz and Shah, 2010; Arshad, 2012). Recent global trends in forest management have focused on the transference of forest management from state authority to local communities through Participatory Forest Management (PFM) (FAO, 2003). PFM provides opportunities to communities living in and around forests to take direct control of the forest. They use and co-manage forest resources with the state authorities on the some fixed cost and benefit sharing mechanisms. Despite the style of participation, ownership, improved local governance, empowerment and poverty alleviation instills the discourse on PFM (Wily *et al.*, 2000; Hobley, 2006). The term PFM is perhaps in a wider sense that is for partnership between various entities and organizations and even for intra-community co-operative arrangements (Rao, 2001; Shahbaz and Shah, 2010; Arshad, 2012). In India according to an estimate more than 35,000 village committees are protecting about 3.5 million hectares of forest, which is 5.5% of total forest cover of India (as cited by Shahbaz and Shah, 2010). PFM is an out-come of several factors including the inability of forest department to prevent the degradation of forest resources or decline in forest cover throughout the country (Balooni, 2002). Forests of Muzaffarabad district are of core importance in the local economy and as well as in

AJK state economy. The main objective of PFM is three fold; to improve forest quality, livelihoods and local governance of natural resources (Mamoona, 2009). PFM can have significant positive impacts especially considering financial, natural, physical, human, political and environmental aspects (Schreckenber *et al.*, 2007).

Four Participatory Forest Management (PFM) projects are currently being implemented in district Muzaffarabad: Integrated Land Management (ILM) project, Poverty Reduction Project (PRP), Reforestation of Blanks and Azad Jammu and Kashmir Community Development Project (AJKCDP). The objective of these projects includes income generation, employment provisions, protection and maintenance of forests. Projects are executed by Forest Department and funded by foreign donors. Though, these projects have been working since last three decades, no quality data is available on the socio-economic assessment of these projects. Thus, there is a need to conduct a research study to fill this gap.

This study is conducted with the aim of assessment of socio-economic of PFM in district Muzaffarabad especially considering different PFM projects. It gives an indication of usefulness of involving local people in PFM in making resources sustainable and it also signifies the role of PFM in increased employment, livelihood and living standards, protection and conservation of forests, social and economic conditions of locals in and around the forest of district Muzaffarabad

The main objective of the study is to assess the socio economic impacts of PFM Projects (Integrated Land Management Project, Poverty Reduction Project, Community Development Project and Reforestation of Blanks) in improving the social conditions of local population and in improving the economic conditions of local population in district Muzaffarabad, AJK.

Acharya (2002) reported that CF intervention in Nepal helped the development of local level institutions for forest management. The users have established forest management research plots at their own initiative, diversified income generating activities and allocated limited use rights to individual members within the CFUGs.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This part is divided in three sections; the first section gives the description of the study area including its brief history, geographical and physical details, land use, forest management and socioeconomic setting of the study area. Second section provides the details of the interventions carried out by various PFM Projects in the area. Third section describes the methodology used for conducting this study (Figure 1).

LOCATION OF THE STUDY AREA

The study area i.e. district Muzaffarabad is one of ten administrative districts in the state of Azad Jammu and Kashmir. It is located between 34° and 35°–10' North latitude and 73°–25' and 74°–30' East longitude. The total area of Muzaffarabad district is 131,190 hectares and is situated at the junction of three rivers: Neelum, Jhelum and Kunhar (GOAJK, 2005). The study area map is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Map of District Muzaffarabad (AJK); Source: www.ajk.gov.pk.

PHYSICAL CONDITIONS AND NATURAL RESOURCES

The topography of the area is mostly rough and mountainous with narrow valleys and steep slopes. The lowest part of district Muzaffarabad is along stream beds and the highest comprised of ridges. The elevation varies from 1,500 m to 3,000 m above sea level (Aslam, 1993; Qadir, 1993; Mamoon, 2009, Shahbaz and Shah, 2010).

Shale and sandstone are the dominant rocks in the soil. Soil is generally deep and poorly drained. But on the southern aspect, it is shallow. Maize, Wheat and Rice are the main crops. Rice is cultivated at lower levels while maize and wheat along the ridges (Shahbaz and Shah, 2010). Among fruits Apple, Apricot, Walnut, Almonds, Plums, Pears, Cherries, Strawberries, Berries and Citrus are common. Soils are shallow on the steeper and southern aspect. The climate is generally more humid on the northern aspect and the vegetation is vigorous.

The district falls into two climatic zones: humid sub-tropical continental high land and humid temperate. It is characterized by extremely low winter temperatures, heavy snowfall, mild summer and torrential monsoon rains often accompanied by hailstorms. Average annual precipitation varies from 1,000 mm to 1,750 mm, about two third of which falls as summer rain and the rest as winter rain and snow. The temperature during November to March is generally below 10C °. Diurnal variation is high (Pakistan Meteorological Department, Lahore, 2009). In Muzaffarabad three rivers Kunhar, Neelum and Jhelum (upper and lower) converge.

POPULATION AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC SETTING

The total population of Muzaffarabad was 607,000 in 2010. The literacy rate is well above 60%, which is significantly higher than the national average of Pakistan (GOAJK, 2010). Eight major tribes are living in the sub-watershed areas. They are Rajput, Gujar, Qureshi, Awan, Abbasi, Mughal, Kiani and Syed. All these possess land which ranges from 1-20 hectares per household. Urdu is widely understood but most of the people speak local languages *Pahari*, *Kashmiri*, and *Hindko* (Mamoona, 2009; Shahbaz and Shah, 2010; Arshad, 2012). The population is mostly rural (i.e. 88%) and depends upon agriculture, livestock and business as local sources of income which are supplemented by working abroad or government or private jobs within the country (Mamoona, 2009; Shahbaz and Shah, 2010; Arshad 2012).

LAND USE AND FOREST RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

The major land uses in the study area are agriculture, grazing and forest. Most of the area of district Muzaffarabad comprises steep slopes, where cultivation is very difficult, however people grow maize, wheat and rice over the slopes. Vegetable is grown in very small quantities except tomatoes and potatoes which are grown in excess and supplied to other areas. Cow dung is exclusively used as farm yard manure. One pair of bullocks and one buffalo is ideal number of livestock per household. Fruit trees like apple, pears, apricot, peach, plum and walnut are planted on small scale. Recently the people have started planting fruit orchards (Shahbaz and Shah, 2010; Arshad 2012). 42.6% of the total geographical area (0.6 million hectares approximately) of Azad State of Jammu & Kashmir is controlled by Forest Department. The per capita standing volume and area are 11.32 cubic meters and 0.2 hectares respectively. Annual wood demand is 1.65 million cubic meters and sustainable production is 0.7 million cubic meters (Aslam, 1993). There are two legal categories of Forests in AJK: Demarcated Forests (State Forests) and Private Forests. Demarcated forests are burdened with local people's rights of timber, fuelwood, grass, water, grazing and many other rights as specified under Forest Regulations II of 1930. These forests are managed under Management Plans. The Private Forests are in very small number, owned by local people and managed by Forest Department (Mamoona, 2009; Shahbaz and Shah, 2010; Arshad, 2012).

Most of the area in Muzaffarabad lies within the Chir pine (*Pinus roxburghii*) zone and this is principal forest type surviving on the slopes. Olives (*Olea ferruginea*) and Kikars (*Acacia modesta*) survive along the river and there are blue pines along the crest of the ridge. Forest fires also cause heavy damage to Chir (*Pinus roxburghii*) and Kail (*Pinus wallichiana*) forests. The area around the Muzaffarabad city is quite barren, although the areas in Neelum towards the north have quite rich vegetation (Mamoona, 2009).

PROJECT INTERVENTIONS

Four PFM projects are currently being implemented in district Muzaffarabad with ultimate goal to conserve and develop forest resources of the area by improving NRM, increasing food security and reducing poverty in the area. These projects include;

- 1- Integrated Land Management Project (ILMP)

- 2- Poverty Reduction Project (PRP).
- 3- Azad Jammu and Kashmir Community Development Project (AJKCDP).
- 4- Reforestation of Blanks

All of these projects carryout interventions to improve the socio-economic condition of the local people and halt environment degradation (Khawaja Nazir Ahmad, Conservator of Forests Muzaffarabad Circle, AJK, pers. comm. Sep. 2012). These projects and their interventions are discussed in detail in this section.

INTEGRATED LAND MANAGEMENT PROJECT (ILMP)

ILMP was prepared by the Forest Department of AJ&K to meet the requirements of fuel wood, stop soil erosion, decrease the unemployment and secure food for food deficit areas. The pilot phase of this project was started in 1982 and assisted by World Food Programme (WFP). Under this project, four ecological zones were selected covering three districts i.e. Muzaffarabad, Rawalakot and Kotli. This pilot phase originally had a planned period of three years ending June 1985. Later on, the project was extended which is still operative. The funding is being made from the resources provided by Government of AJ&K, WFP (Food Stamps) and other bilateral donors. WFP is providing 30% of its share in the shape of cash to meet the cash requirements of the activities. Community member are contributing in shape of cash or labour up to 20% of the cost estimates of the field activities (Forest Department Azad Jammu & Kashmir, 2004).

ILMP has three components.

- i- Creating Assets for Rural Women (CARW)
- ii- Community Based Livelihood Rehabilitation Project (CBLRP)
- iii- Protracted Recovery and Relief Operation (PRRO)

Creating Assets for Rural Women (CARW)

Creating Assets for Rural Women (CARW) was instigated in 2004-05 as a five year plan intervention. WFP and the Government of AJ&K jointly provided the budget. (Naseer, 2010).

Creation of Social Assets: SMU has established for social mobilization and community organization. This unit works under the overall control, guidance and supervision of Project Director and Divisional Forest Officer. Female Social Organizers are responsible for the creation of female COs and their related matters (Forest Department Azad Jammu & Kashmir, 2004).

Creation of Economic Assets: Communities have been supported from the project for income generation activities both financially and technically in different fields of specialization. These include:

- i- Small scale enterprise development packages
- ii- Livestock development packages
- iii- Poultry development packages
- iv- Apiculture development packages

Creation of Physical Assets: A range of activities has been implemented under creation of physical assets. These include land rehabilitation and soil conservation works, small scale physical infrastructure development schemes such as water channels, bridle paths, school building, dispensary and water supply schemes, water

harvesting structures and establishment of training and display centre (Forest Department Azad Jammu & Kashmir, 2004).

Protracted Recovery and Relief Operation (PRRO)

This intervention under ILMP was started after the devastating earthquake of Oct.8, 2005. The project area consists of the most food deprived parts (union councils) of the study area. Almost all the activities are same as CARW project but area is different. Instead of food stamps and cash, raw food is given for work. This food basket contains 2.70 kg wheat flour, 0.30 kg is pulses, 0.18 kg oil and 0.03 kg salt (Forest Department Azad Jammu & Kashmir, 2004).

Community Based Livelihood Rehabilitation Project (CBLRP)

CBLRP is the third component of Integrated Land Management Project. This project is financed by Swedish International Development Agency (SIDA) and technical assistance is provided by Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO). The project activities include soil conservation works (stone work such as check dams, retaining walls, gabion, terracing and bio-engineering works like wattling, brush layering and palisade), plantation, natural regeneration, seedling distribution, reseeding of new grasses, cattle ponds construction, orchard raising and training (Forest Department Azad Jammu & Kashmir, 2004).

Water Tank Constructed by ILM at Haryala Gujran Village

Cattle Pond at Lawasi Village

Land Rehabilitation Work at Kohala Road, Muzaffarabad (a)

Land Rehabilitation Work at Kohala Road, Muzaffarabad (b)

Figure 2: Pictorial view of Different sites of PFM projects.

PROGRESS OF ILMP, MUZAFFARABAD

From 1981 to 2003 following physical targets are achieved (Table 1).

Table 1: Physical Achievements.

Sr. No.	Activity	Units	Achievements
1	Planting	Acre	31920
2	Maintenance of Planting	Acre	4789
3	Soil Conservation Works	Million cft	19.0818
4	Cattle Ponds	No	107
5	Water Springs	No	96
6	Planting of Forest Trees	Acre	484
7	Contour Planting	Km	139
8	Road Construction	Km	23
9	Bridle Path	Km	45

10	Sowing	Acre	1270
11	Community Development Schemes	No	32
12	Training (Male & Female)	No	3117
13	Socio-Development Packages	No	75
14	Poultry Development	No	36

Source: Progress Reports Forest Department, 2004

POVERTY REDUCTION PROJECT (PRP) MUZAFFARABAD

This project is funded by Govt. of Pakistan through Ministry of Environment, Islamabad and Azad government of the State of Jammu and Kashmir. The AJK-PRP covers entire AJK except areas covered by WFP assisted Integrated Land Management Projects. The whole AJK is divided into 351 self-draining sub-watersheds. The selected sub-watershed is treated on entirely basis, in a progression of activities starting from upper reaches where surface water flow starts, regulating it through the hill slopes to valley bottom down where it finally accumulates into streams, employing bio-engineering control measures, recommended land use options and participatory management of natural resources with the objectives of environmental rehabilitation and checking sediments into flow of Mangla Reservoir. The project is operative in district Muzaffarabad (Forest Department Azad Jammu & Kashmir, 2004).

PROGRESS OF PRP, MUZAFFARABAD

From 2007 to 2010 following physical targets are achieved (Table 2).

Table 2: Physical Achievements

Sr. No.	Activity	Units	Achievements
1	Planting	Acre	2267
2	Cultural Operations	Acre	3925
3	Seedling Production	M.No	3.279
4	Loose Stone Walls	M.cft	0.084

Source: Progress Reports Forest Department, 2010

AZAD JAMMU & KASHMIR COMMUNITY DEVELOPMENT PROJECT (AJKCDP)

This programme was started in 1992 which is sponsored by International Fund for Agriculture Development (IFAD). World Food Programme (WFP) and Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) are contributing financial resources to the project (Sabir Trimzi, Chief planning officer, Muzaffarabad, AJK, pers. comm. Sep. 2012).

The overall programme objective is to improve the wellbeing of the rural poor through consolidation, strengthening and expansion of gender sensitive community based participatory village development planning, implementation and monitoring (Forest Department Azad Jammu & Kashmir, 2004).

The project interventions include:

- Strengthening the role and capabilities of existing community organizations (COs) and establishing new COs to extend the development benefits to the target group on a sustainable basis;

- Establishing the basis for successful devolution process by promoting effective governance, transparency and accountability through improvements in operational, financial and relationships between central and local institutions; and
- Improvement of natural resource management and expand social and economic infrastructure necessary to increase the income and employment opportunities and reduce the conditions of poverty for the vulnerable segments of the communities.

Reforestation of Blanks

This project was started in 1967. The main objective is filling up the blanks area in the demarcated forest by reforestation and afforestation. The community participation in the project is very low as it is working in state forests where no community is involved in management or protection of forests.

Methodology

This section describes in detail the research methodology applied in this study. The section has been organized into two major sections namely; conceptual frame work and research method. The research method used in carrying out the research is presented in three sub sections namely: Sampling, Data Collection and Data Analysis.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK OF THE RESEARCH

The current study focuses on assessing the socioeconomic impacts of participatory forest management regimes in Muzaffarabad, Azad Jammu Kashmir. Impact assessment is the process of identifying the anticipated or actual impacts of a development intervention on those social, economic and factors for which the intervention is designed to affect or may inadvertently affect and the intended beneficiaries (Mamoona, 2009). The research focused on the impacts of different activities carried out by different projects in the study area. The conceptual frame work (Figure 4) describes that different socio-economic factors and program activities had brought about different impacts.

Figure 3. Conceptual frame work of the study.

RESEARCH METHOD

The research methods used in carrying out the research are described in this section.

Sampling

The study aimed to assess the impact of Participatory Forest Management Programs/Projects implemented in Muzaffarabad District of Azad Jammu Kashmir. A purposive selection of research site was made on the basis of three parameters and criteria i.e. suitability in line with the research objective, maximum forest cover and socio-geographical conditions (Mamoona, 2009; Shahbaz and Shah, 2010). The population for this research was household heads in Muzaffarabad District of Azad Jammu Kashmir (AJK). The unit of analysis was the list of households in study areas (Mamoona, 2009).

A multistage random sampling technique was applied to select households/respondents. The population of Muzaffarabad was 607000 in 2015. As there are almost seven persons in a house, so the number of households was determined to be 88000. Sample size was determined by using the formula:

Sample Size

$$n = \frac{Z^2 * (p) * (1-p)}{c^2}$$

Where:

Z = Z value (1.96 for 95% confidence level)

p = Expected proportion in population (70% is most conservative) (.7 used for sample size needed)

c = confidence interval (10% in this case), expressed as decimal

Source: Creative Research System, <http://www.surveysystem.com/sscalc.htm>

The sample size was found to be 86. However 90 respondents were interviewed in the field. Thus, the sampling intensity is 0.1%. The sample units were selected using multistage random sampling. In first stage, 3 UCs were randomly selected. In second stage, 4 villages were selected in each UC. Finally, 7 households were randomly chosen in every selected village. Thus, a total of 90 respondents were selected for interview. The villages were selected at random from list of union councils (UCs).

Data Collection

Two types of data were used for conducting this study: primary and secondary data. Primary data was collected from randomly selected villages by interviewing respondents personally using a semi structured questionnaire. Secondary data was collected from various sources including books, journals, technical reports, websites and project records.

The questionnaire was prepared in English. However, during the interview, the question were asked in local language and translated into English. The questionnaire was pre-tested before the actual data was collected.

Data Analysis

The data was processed by computer using statistical programs including MS Excel and SPSS version 20. Using this statistical package, some cross tabulations were also

carried out to show the outcome of computations and a variety of statistical analyses were applied. However, the analysis was kept simple to attain the purpose and scope of the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the overall results of the study, compares them, and discusses and analyses the findings. The section is organized into four sections; Section 1 discusses socio-demographic data, Section 2 describes participation in the PFM projects activities, Section 3 explains socio-economic impacts and Section 4 will show the effect of PFM on environment.

SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC DATA

General Characteristics of the Respondents

All the respondents were permanent residents of the area. Majority of the respondents (90%) were male who were also heads of their households followed by (10%) female. The gender-wise distribution of the respondents is given in Figure 4. The household respondents represented both gender with males (90%) dominating in the study data. In this culture, male (husband) is the head of the household and female (usually wife) takes position in the absence of husband. That's why some females (10%) were also interviewed. 59% respondents belong to the area where ILM is working, 25% are from PRP area while 8% respondents belong to CDP and Reforestation areas.

Land Ownership and Categories of Landholding

The survey revealed that majority of respondents (83%) were land owners, while only 7% respondents were landless.

Age Class Distribution

The survey found that the village household size of the sampled households is 7. Average number of male per household is 4 and female is 3. Majority (60%) of the respondents belong to age class 41-60 years followed by age class 21-40 years.

Literacy Rate

The overall literacy rate in the area is 93% which is quite high. Out of 90 respondents interviewed, 44% were primary, 32% were secondary, and 17% were Graduate while remaining 7% of the respondents were illiterate.

Occupation of Respondents

As for the occupation is concerned, the study reveals that there is a variety of occupations which the people of the study area has adopted. The survey revealed that the occupation of the majority of respondents (27%) was Agriculture followed by Government service (22%), private service (5%), Business (20%), Forestry (12%), Other (11%) and Foreign Remittance (3%)

Figure 4: General Characteristics of the Respondents

PARTICIPATION OF LOCAL COMMUNITY IN PFM PROJECT ACTIVITIES

Knowledge of PFM Projects

The finding of the study reveals that majority (90%) of the respondents know about PFM working in their area. This indicates that the PFM projects have reached to the most of the people in the area. This higher level of awareness could lead to the success of PFM interventions.

Presence of Forest

The study reveals that forests exist in near vicinity of the villages. All the respondents replied that forests are present near their villages. The private forests are managed by community or people themselves under PFM programme. The communal lands are owned by government and managed and utilized by the community. The study revealed that in all the survey area forest exists adjacent to the villages. Significant number of respondents (59%) revealed that existing forests are owned and managed by government in traditional style, whereas 10% state that forests are owned and managed by local community. However 26% state that forests are owned by the government and managed by local community while 5% did not know about the management.

Participation of People in PFM Activities

Majority of the people not only know about PFM but have also participated in the PFM activities. The result of the survey shows that 77% respondent have participated in the project activities. Thus, their views represent a fair assessment of the project success or failure in the area.

Level of Participation

The study shows that a large number of respondents have participated in different activities organized by ILM, PRP and/or CDP. Respondents have different level of participation in the project activities. 22% of the respondents have participated in the agricultural activities and 19% are engaged in CO membership. 18% are involved in various training programmes. Only 4% of the respondents have participated in planting activities. On the other hand 16% have participated in other activities like Access Road, Bridal Path, Water Tank, Irrigation Channel, and Diversion Channel. The low level of respondents' participation in plantation is mainly due to the reason that landholdings are not enough and plantation requires skilled workers for plantation activities. For the success of PFM, there is a need to involve more local people in plantation activities

Figure 5: Participation of local community in PFM Project Activities

Community Organization and CO Membership

Social mobilization is a tool to ensure maximum participation of local communities in the PFM Programmes. Under the three projects, local people have been organized in the form of community organization (CO). Male and Female COs have been established in the area. Various questions were asked during the survey to know the level of participation and effectiveness of the COs in the area. The survey shows that 88% of the respondents were aware about the establishment of COs in their areas while only 3% of the respondents denied the presence of COs in their area whereas 9% have no idea about Cos. About 88% of the respondents reported that CO

membership is open to all villagers. Rest of the respondents was unable to respond to this question.

Female Community Organizations

Women play important role in natural resource management (NRM) in the area. They collected fuel wood, grasses and medicinal plants from the forests and are involved in various farming activities and livestock rearing. It is, thus essential that women be involved in project activities. For this purpose, female COs have been established in the area. The respondents were asked questions to get their perception about female COs in the area. Out of the 90 respondents interviewed, 55% were aware about the female COs working in their area. While 28% are denied about the female COs working in their area. Rest of the respondents (18%) have no idea about female COs. This data indicates that female COs are not very effective or they are confined to only females. Consequently, male respondents are unaware about their activities.

Participation Opportunities

85% of the respondents reported that all the members of CO have equal opportunities of participation while only 2% did not agree it and 13% have no idea about participation in the Cos.

The overall analysis of the information provided by the respondents indicates that community participation is significantly high. Majority of the respondents have physically participated in the project interventions.

Formation Process of the COs

Majority (83%) of the respondents are happy with the formation process of the CO while only 5% are not very happy with this process. Rest of the respondents (12%) had no idea about the CO formation. The respondents also made some suggestions to bring about some positive changes in the process of CO formation. They stressed for decreasing the role of forest department (FD) in CO formation and fully democratizing the election process for the CO formation.

Extent to which the Identified Problems are solved by COs

The study attempted to determine the effectiveness of COs in solving the community problems. The study revealed that COs are good enough to solve the problems as identified by the community. 13% responded that CO is very good, 58% replied in good (which means that COs are active and helping in the uplift of people), 19% replied in average while 8% don't have any idea whereas only 1% replied in no. Thus an overwhelming majority of the respondents showed their satisfaction about the performance of COs in their areas.

Figure 6: Community Organization and CO Membership

SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACTS OF PFM

Importance of Forest for Livelihood Support

The respondents were asked about the importance of forest for their livelihood support. All (100%) the respondents were of the view that forest is important for their livelihood support (Table 3).

Table 3: Ranks of Importance Items in the Livelihood Support beneficial at House Hold Level.

Sr. No.	Benefits	Firstly Important	Secondly Important	Thirdly Important	Fourthly Important	Fifthly Important	Sixthly Important	Seventhly Important	Eighthly Important	Total
1.	Fuel wood energy	67 (74)	17 (19)	5 (6)	-	-	-	1 (1)	-	90 (100)
2.	Construction material	20 (22)	45 (50)	24 (27)	1 (1)	-	-	-	-	90 (100)
3.	Food & fruits	-	45 (50)	5 (6)	1 (1)	21 (23)	8 (9)	9 (10)	1 (1)	90 (100)
4.	Spiritual & cultural services	13 (14)	6 (7)	1 (1)	25 (28)	16 (18)	15 (17)	14 (15)	-	90 (100)
5.	Medicinal	-	2 (2)	2 (2)	15 (17)	10 (11)	14 (16)	13 (14)	34 (38)	90 (100)
6.	Fodder	15 (17)	21 (23)	45 (50)	5 (6)	3 (3)	1 (1)	-	-	90 (100)
7.	Beekeeping activities	-	-	-	1 (1)	1 (1)	20 (24)	26 (28)	42 (46)	90 (100)
8.	Environmental good & services	30 (33)	21 (24)	20 (23)	12 (13)	3 (3)	2 (2)	2 (2)	-	90 (100)

*Frequency (percentage)

Respondents were asked to rank the given potential benefits accrued from the forest at household level according to the importance. The majority (74%) of respondents marked fuel wood energy as the foremost important for their livelihood support, 19% respondents termed it as secondly important of their livelihood support. For construction material, 22% respondents considered it the most important, 50% respondents considered it second most important, while 27% respondents gave it third important source of livelihood support. Fodder was the third important for the respondents and was found most important for 17%, while 23% considered it second most important whereas 50% considered it the third most important. Spiritual and the cultural festivals were found fourth most important 14% respondents and second important by 7% respondents. Food and fruits were found fourth important.

The respondents were asked about the requirement of timber/year. Majority (41%) replies that they need 10 cft of timber every year for maintenance of their

houses which shows that the quantity of timber required is not high although it is one of the most important commodities for rural life in the area.

CAUSES OF DEGRADATION

When the respondents were asked about the activities which led to the degradation of the forest in area, majority of the respondents (40%) told that forests were degraded due to combined effect of over harvesting and grazing, over exploitation of forest for fire/fuel wood, frequently occurred bush fire from various causes and encroachment for cultivation and settlements in the forest area. However, over harvesting and over grazing were termed as the main reason behind forest degradation as reported by 21% of the respondents. Out the of the total 90 respondents, 16% told that the reason of degradation was frequently occurred bush fire from various causes and 11% told that the sole cause of the degradation of the forest was over exploitation for fire wood.

Figure 7: Timber Requirement Per Year (left), Causes of Degradation (right)

INCOME FROM THE SALE OF FOREST PRODUCE

Respondents were asked about the income contribution from the sale of forest produce. 42% of the respondents were getting income from the sale of forest produce. Out of those, 49% of the respondents were earning up to Rs. 10000/- per year from the sale forest produce, 17% were getting Rs. 11000-30000/- per year, 12% were gaining Rs. 31000-50000/- per year, 10% were accruing Rs. 51000-100000/- per year, 7% were getting Rs. 101000-150000/- per year, 3% were getting Rs. 1510000-200000/- per year and 2% were accruing Rs. 201000-250000/- per year from the sale of forest produce.

The analysis of the data indicates that forests are contributing in the household income. However, for majority of the respondents income is low i.e. up to Rs. 30000/- per year for 66% of the respondents. The previous study (Shahbaz and Shah, 2010) shows that 72% of the respondents of the area were getting income from the

sale of the forest produce. Thus, the development of the alternate livelihood strategies could be possible to divert pressure from the forests of the area.

FOREST IN LOCALITY IMPROVED TO MEET THE REQUIREMENTS AFTER PFM

Respondents were asked the question that if the forests in area were improved to meet the requirements after PFM. A vast majority (77%) of the respondent were of the view that forests are improved to meet the requirements of timber and fuel wood.

ACCESS TO LIVELIHOOD SUPPORT INTERVENTIONS

The respondents were asked that how they got access to livelihood through PFM projects. The significant portion of respondents (62%) told that PFM had helped them in improvement of fuel wood and fodder resources, 17% respondents told that PFM had helped them in infrastructure development, 11% of respondents told that they had got different employment / labour opportunities and 10% told that PFM had created household business opportunities for them.

Figure 8: Socio-Economic Impacts of PFM.

IMPACTS OF PFM ON LIVESTOCK & AGRICULTURE

The study reveals that there is an enormous impact of PFM on agriculture and livestock. Respondents were asked about their livestock that how many domesticated animals they have before and after PFM; also they were asked about the position of agricultural crops before and after PFM. A bi-variate test (T-Test) was applied to check the significance of PFM on different items of livestock and agricultural crops (Appendix II).

The effect of PFM on the number (0.947) and income of sheep/goat (1.000) is insignificant as the difference in the last column of the table above is more than 0.05. The effect of PFM on the number of cow (0.030) and income from the cow (0.024) is significant. It means that the number of the cow and income from them was increased. There was no effect of PFM on the number of Bull/Ox (0.056) and income from them (0.141). The number (0.000) of buffalo and income (0.000) from those buffalos increased significantly after PFM. So, there was a very significant effect of PFM on the increase in number of buffalo and also increased income from them. There was also a significant effect of PFM on Poultry.

The effect of PFM on agricultural crops like wheat and maize was significant. The production (0.010 for wheat and 0.000 for maize) and income from both these crops (0.04 for wheat and 0.000 for maize) increased significantly due to PFM activities. However, the effect of PFM on crops like rice, vegetables and production of fruit and income from them is insignificant. So, there was no increase in the production of those items.

Increase in Income

Direct increase in household income due to project interventions is the key indicator of the success of the project in the socio-economic uplift of the area. Respondents were asked about to determine if there is any increase in income due to PFM. Majority (76%) confirmed increase in their income level due to PFM interventions.

Training or Packages under PFM

Respondents were asked that whether they got any package or have done any training. Majority (82%) of the respondents replied in no. Only 6% of the respondents got Livestock package while the percentage of the respondents engaged in nursery or vocational training was insufficient. Respondents were also asked that if the said training or package was useful or not. Majority (90%) of the respondents have claimed that the training was not useful.

Figure 9: Training or Packages under PFM.

The data shows that the capacity building components of the PFM are very weak and they have failed to reach the significant portion of the community.

Accrued Synergies at Village Level

The study revealed number of important synergies beneficial at village level, which have been grouped into four different portfolios namely environmental, social, economic and human based portfolios. However, we have dealt with all these benefits collectively. The respondents were inquired about benefits accrued at village level from PFM; sizeable majority (80%) said that benefits had been accrued at village level. However, 13% respondents opposed that any benefit had been acquired at village level and 7% respondents were having no idea about the statement.

Benefits Accrued at Village Level

The participants were asked to list the benefits accrued in all four categories and ranked them according to their importance. Maximum 28% respondents ranked forest cover improvement as the most important benefit accrued at village level through PFM projects, 20% respondents said that it was clean water and environment which was most important benefit accrued at village level, 12% respondents said that employment opportunities were firstly important, 8% marked improved standard

living and first important benefit and just 6% respondents ranked infrastructure development as the first most important benefit accrued at village level. The 25% respondents ranked employment opportunities as second most important benefit, 19% respondent ranked clean water and environment, 17% marked forest cover improvement, 13% marked improvement standard of living and only 7% ranked infrastructure development as second most important benefit accrued at village.

Table 4: Ranking of Benefits Accrued at Village Level by the Local People

S. No.	Benefits	Ranking				
		Firstly Important	Secondly Important	Thirdly Important	Fourthly Important	Fifthly Important
1.	Infrastructure development	5 (6)	6 (7)	8 (9)	7 (8)	48 (53)
2.	Forest cover improvement	28 (31)	15 (17)	11 (12)	12 (13)	3 (4)
3.	Employment opportunities	11 (12)	23 (25)	21 (23)	10 (11)	2 (2)
4.	Clean water & environment	20 (22)	17 (19)	22 (25)	9 (10)	1 (1)
5.	Improved standard of living	7 (8)	12 (13)	10 (11)	32 (36)	17 (19)
6.	N.A.	19 (21)	17 (19)	18 (20)	20 (22)	19 (21)
	Total	90 (100)	90 (100)	90 (100)	90 (100)	90 (100)

Social Conditions affected by PFM environmental interventions

Information was also collected to assess the impacts of PFM projects on environment. This section gives the detail of the respondents' views about this aspect.

Public Awareness about Environment

Respondents were asked whether public awareness about environmental issues has increased after PFM or not? Majority (63%) replied in positive.

Condition of Forest

As the ultimate objectives of all the PFM interventions is to achieve forest resource conservation, question were asked to get the respondents views about changes brought about in forestry sector. However, it is essential to know the condition of the forest before initiation of PFM and the reasons behind any forest degradation, if there. Majority of the respondents (60%) were with the view that condition of the forest area before PFM was much degraded while 21% respondents told it was moderately degraded whereas 17% considered it to be slightly degraded and just 1% respondents were also unaware of the situation or voted against it.

Impacts of PFM on Forest Resources

After ascertaining that the forests were degraded before PFM and identifying the factors for such degradation, the respondents were asked to comment on the change brought about by PFM. Almost 81% of the respondents claimed that the condition of forest has been improved after PFM while 29% refused this claim.

Figure 10: Social Conditions affected by PFM environmental interventions.

Indicator for Improvement

Out of the total 90 respondents, 51% told that the indicators of improvement were the growing stock with vigorous species regeneration and controlled illegal activities like grazing, cutting, encroachment and fire etc., while 20% respondents indicated that

more control on illegal activities (grazing, cutting, encroachment and fire) had played a pivotal role in the improvement of the forest.

Reasons for No Improvement

When the 9% respondents refusing any improvement after PFM were inquired about the reasons for no improvement, 51% respondents were of the view that lack of awareness was the reason for no improvement, 12% told that people involvement at all levels of PFM was not assured whereas only 26% claimed that reason for no improvement was that PFM was not applied in its real sense while 11% did not know the reasons.

Satisfaction of People with PFM

The respondents were inquired whether they are happy with PFM or not. About 61% respondents told that they were happy but needed some more improvement, 9% respondents were not happy with PFM at all and needed radical improvements, 28% respondents told that they were very happy with PFM projects and there was no need of improvement whereas 2% had no idea. This indicates that the overall performance of the PFM is satisfactory as most of the people are happy with project interventions. However, there is a room for improvement which should be utilized.

Suggestion for Improvement

The respondents were also asked to suggest measures for the improvement of PFM. Most of the respondents even those who were very happy with the PFM also gave suggestions that how improvement in PFM programmes could be brought. Almost 6% of the respondents needed the improvement or change in the form of local communities empowerment, 6% required more communication, transparency and accountability, majority (33%) suggested more incentives / revenue to villages, 12% suggested more access and control over resources by locals and another 12% suggested that all of the above mentioned improvements are required.

Figure 11: Impacts of PFM on Forest Resources.

Impact of PFM on Soil Erosion

Soil erosion is an important indicator of environmental degradation. Its control is must for sustainability. Respondents were asked if soil erosion increased or decreased after PFM. Majority (79%) of the responded replied that the erosion has decreased. However 17% were not satisfied and answered that there was no effect of Participatory Forest Management on the control of soil erosion and 4% were uncertain about this aspect of PFM. It can be concluded from the data that the PFM project have brought a positive change in soil conservation in the area. This change is mainly due to plantation and soil conservation works conducted in the area.

Impact of PFM on Perennial Water Flow

Perennial water flow is essential for sustainability of water resources. Regular supply of water is the ultimate object of a watershed management regime. The Participatory Forest Management interventions must lead to a positive impact on water flow in the area. The respondents were asked to comment on impact of Participatory Forest Management on perennial water flow. 41% respondents thought that perennial water flow has improved after PFM intervention while 45% did not think so and 14% were uncertain about any change.

Effect of PFM Biodiversity

Biodiversity conservation is one of the main goals of sustainable forest management. In order to determine the impact of Participatory Forest Management on biodiversity, the respondents were asked to get their views on this aspect of Participatory Forest Management. However, majority (86%) was uncertain about the impact of Participatory Forest Management on bio-diversity. 11% considered that biodiversity increased after Participatory Forest Management whereas 3% did not support this

position. Thus, it is clear that the impacts of Participatory Forest Management are not significant to be noticed by ordinary observer. Only biodiversity experts or quantitative survey in this field can determine the impact of Participatory Forest Management on biodiversity in the area.

Impact of PFM on Land Sliding

Land sliding is a common phenomenon in the study area. It was further increased after the 2005 earthquake and the hazards were increased several times. The PFM projects have tried to treat these slides and increase vegetation cover in the vulnerable areas to reduce the hazards of land sliding. A vast majority (91%) was certain that land sliding had reduced after PFM. 7% considered that land sliding did not decrease after the interventions of PFM activities whereas 2% of the respondents were uncertain.

Impact of PFM on Floods

One of the main objective of the PFM to increase the vegetation cover in the uphill catchment areas to reduce flooding in the downstream areas. The respondents were asked to determine the impacts of PFM on flood situation. Majority (66%) of the respondents were certain that flood had been reduced after PFM interventions. 29% considered that there was no change in floods after the interventions of PFM whereas 5% of the respondents were uncertain.

Impact of PFM on Drinking Water

Water quality is directly or indirectly affected by PFM interventions. Direct effect is improvement in water supply pipes or water tanks whereas indirect effect is due to increase in vegetative cover in the catchment area or near water source. The study revealed that the quality of drinking water had improved after PFM interventions. Majority (61%) of the respondents were certain that the quality of drinking water had improved after PFM. However, 16% considered that there was no improvement in the quality of water whereas 23% of the respondents were uncertain about any such change.

Figure 12: Impact of PFM on Perennial Water Flow, Biodiversity, Land Sliding, Floods, Drinking Water .

CONCLUSIONS

The following recommendations are made from this research in order to improve the participatory forestry management regime and to ensure the maximum positive socio-economic impacts which will lead to forest resource conservation in the area.

- Even though the project interventions have resulted in socio-economic benefits, there is a need to increase the tangible benefits to the households. This can be achieved through encouragement of alternative income generation activities such as incentives for increasing agricultural production, beekeeping projects, agro forestry, kitchen gardening and value addition to the local products.
- Project activities should focus on developing local institutional capacity to achieve the objectives of forest management and rural development. Moreover to negotiate better benefits from PFM regime, the local people have to be actively involved not

only at the information receiving and implementation level but at decision making level as well.

- The participation of local communities in plantation and other forest management activities is very low. There is a need to enhance the skills of local communities in nursery raising, planting, medicinal plant harvesting to explore the full potentials of PFM.
- There is a need to give central importance to the involvement of the local communities in forest protection, conservation and sustainable development. Other activities should be tailored in such a way to achieve the goal of forest conservation.
- Subsidized fuel should be made available to the people of study area. This will reduce the pressure of fuel wood extraction on the forest.
- There should be more emphasis on the production of poultry chicks and raising of livestock such as buffalo to supplement the income on sustained basis.
- Fruit tree species suitable to the area should be made available and grown. This will not only give a vegetative cover to the soil but also supplement the income of the households.
- Training and education of the improved practices in agriculture, forestry and livestock should be arranged for the farmers of the area.

Finally, it is suggested that future research should focus on the quantitative assessment of the impacts of PFM at field level including the assessment of change in forest cover, control on deforestation and degradation and change in biodiversity due to PFM.

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